

Between the Belt and Road and the Indo-Pacific: Lithuania's Strategic Reorientation

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Abstract: This paper examines the evolving dynamics of Lithuania's engagement with China's Belt and Road Initiative, analysing how Lithuania has navigated the intersection of economic opportunities, security concerns, and value-based foreign policy. Lithuania's initial participation in the BRI framework was a pragmatic attempt to diversify trade partnerships, attract investment, and enhance global connectivity. However, when these expectations failed to materialise, and concerns arose regarding the strategic implications of Chinese interest in key infrastructure, the BRI was increasingly framed not as an economic opportunity but as a potential security threat. Although this development is consistent with other CEE countries, Lithuania stands out as a small state that has coupled its reassessment of China policy with the adoption of an Indo-Pacific strategy, thereby embracing a competing framework to conceptualise regional order. Drawing on an inductive analysis of government documents and interviews, this paper demonstrates how Lithuania exercised its agency by shifting from engagement with the BRI to alignment with like-minded partners in the Indo-Pacific. The findings suggest that Lithuania's case demonstrates how small states can adapt foreign policy through pragmatic risk management and values-based positioning.

Introduction

Amongst European Union (EU) member states, Lithuania stands out as a case of a small country that initially engaged with the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) as a pragmatic effort to enhance trade and investment (e.g. Kavalski 2018). However, it later changed its approach significantly, emerging as one of the most prominent critics of China within the EU. During this shift, the idea of increased economic cooperation with China and participation in the BRI largely faded from the focus of Lithuania's political elite. It became far less visible in broader discussions while being reframed through the lens of security concerns and the risks of interference in critical infrastructure and national decision-making (Assaf 2010; Jüris 2023).

As part of this reorientation, Lithuania published an Indo-Pacific strategy (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Lithuania 2023), formalising its intent to diversify its economic relations from China and to align more closely with the Indo-Pacific framework. Unlike the BRI, which represents China's effort to build new connectivity corridors under its leadership, the Indo-Pacific framework is promoted by the United States and is often perceived as a counterweight to China's rise and as a competing vision of economic and security order (Heiduk 2022; Pugliese 2024). Lithuania's initial goals of economic diversification and international connectivity previously associated with China were thus formally situated within the Indo-Pacific framework, which aligns more closely with its value-driven foreign policy and transatlantic alliance framework. This shift allowed Lithuania to position itself as a proactive, value-aligned partner within a broader network of like-minded states. Publishing this strategy, Lithuania sought to establish new trade and investment relationships while leveraging its anti-China stance to enhance its visibility and alignment in the international arena.

This development is puzzling for two reasons. First, Lithuania aligned itself with China's connectivity project through the 16+1 in 2012. It signed a Memorandum of Understanding with Beijing on the BRI in 2017 (Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas 2017), similar to most Central and Eastern European (CEE) states. Over time, many of these countries reassessed their positions and grew more sceptical of China, a trend that scholars often attribute to disappointment with the limited economic returns of the cooperation (e.g. Kavalski 2021; Turcsányi 2020). However, that alone does not explain the growing security perception of China present in the Lithuanian case.

What further sets Lithuania apart is that it did not merely downgrade its participation in China-led frameworks quietly. It was the first to formally leave the (at that point) 17+1, followed by the two Baltic states, while the remaining 14 states stayed in this largely stalled format (Hulička 2023, Interview #6). What is particularly striking is that Lithuania, as a small state, chose to make this move publicly, drawing significant international attention.

Second, Lithuania is one of the two 16+1 states (apart from the Czech Republic) that have formally adopted an Indo-Pacific strategy within the context of shifting relations with China, thereby officially embracing the concept of the Indo-Pacific. Indo-Pacific is a contested regional framework promoted by actors such as Japan and the United States, emerging as an alternative to the traditional Asia-Pacific label. It spans from the eastern coast of Africa to the Pacific Islands, highlighting India as a central actor, and is often seen as a counter to China and the BRI, promoting a Free and Open Indo-Pacific grounded in international law, democratic values, and a rules-based order (Heiduk 2022; Massot and Tiberghien 2024; Medcalf 2019; Poon et al. 2024). However, as a smaller country, distant from the Indo-Pacific region, Lithuania has limited material opportunities to engage there actively.

That raises questions about the motivations behind this reorientation and broader questions about how small states can exercise agency in their relations with China, and why such behaviour is inconsistent across the Baltic region, or among other small states participating in the 16+1 framework. This paper thus aims to contribute to this special issue by addressing two central research questions: (1) How has Lithuania's initial participation in, and subsequent disengagement from, the BRI reshaped its diplomatic, transnational economic, and social spatial linkages? (2) How has Lithuania, as a small state, appeared to extend its power through its engagement and eventual distancing from the BRI and its strategic realignment toward the Indo-Pacific?

To answer these questions, the paper is grounded in small state theoretical debates, primarily focused on agency and adaptive strategies of small states in international relations. It engages with the conceptual framework of this special issue and addresses the three broad themes of space, power, and governance. Space is understood geographically and as the production of economic and diplomatic linkages that situate small states within broader transnational frameworks. For Lithuania, participation in the BRI initially promised new spatial connections beyond Europe. Later, these were reconfigured through its withdrawal from Chinese-led initiatives and subsequent alignment with the Indo-Pacific concept. Power is approached less as material capacity and more as agency, exercised through discursive framing and normative alignment. Lithuania's shift from presenting China and the BRI as economic opportunities to framing them as security risks, while

embracing the Indo-Pacific concept, illustrates how small states can leverage discursive and normative tools to amplify their international presence. Finally, governance refers to the institutional and regulatory environments that shape the scope of engagement with external initiatives. In the Lithuanian case, EU membership provided a framework that constrained the implementation of BRI projects, thereby making governance of the projects less contentious.

Firstly, the paper offers an outline of the perception of Lithuania as a small state within the International Relations (IR) literature and provides an overview of the theoretical framework and methodology. The following section then examines Lithuania's initial engagement with the BRI. While referring to the conceptual framework of this special issue, it traces the growing disillusionment and the emergence of security and normative concerns. It analyses the post-2020 foreign policy shift and the adoption of the Indo-Pacific strategy. The paper argues that Lithuania's shift from the BRI to the Indo-Pacific exemplifies how small states can discursively reposition themselves to assert agency and reinforce alliances.

Lithuania and the Small State Debate: Beyond Structural Constraints

Although there is no universally agreed-upon definition of a small state, Lithuania is commonly understood as one within the academic debate (e.g. Andrijauskas 2024; Collins and O'Brien 2023; Isoda 2024; Park and Jakstaite-Confortola 2021). This classification is based not only on quantitative criteria, such as population, territory size, or gross domestic product (GDP) (e.g. Park and Jakstaite-Confortola 2021), but also on qualitative indicators, including identity (Bukovskis and Livdanska 2024) or self-perception (Andrijauskas 2024). The prior literature defines Lithuania's 'smallness', for example, relationally, in contrast to neighbouring Russia (Lingevičius 2019), or as one of the smaller member states of the EU (Lamoreaux and Galbreath 2008). Although this understanding is not uniform, Lithuania is frequently portrayed as a small state within its domestic leadership discourse, not only due to its size and capacities, but also in response to the security threat posed by Russia (Lingevičius 2019). In this sense, for the purposes of this paper, its small state profile is only reinforced regarding its unbalanced trade relations with China or the possibility of having a sizable presence in the Indo-Pacific.

However, within the academic literature on small states and Lithuania's domestic discourse, smallness is not necessarily a determinant of weakness. Rather than being constrained by their structural limitations, small states are often seen as capable of exercising agency through distinct foreign policy strategies. Scholars suggest that such states may engage in norm entrepreneurship, pursue strategic multilateralism, or align with larger powers to enhance their influence on the

international stage (Long 2016; Thorhallsson 2019). Thus, previous scholarship has examined Lithuania's ability to improve its status in international relations by taking a strong stance towards the Belarusian regime and supporting the democratic political opposition in Belarus, or by consistently expressing support for the Eastern Partnership countries (Bukovskis and Livdanska 2024; Milta 2015). It has also been noted that Lithuania has been able to challenge China by offering strong support to Taiwan, demonstrating the potential of small states to impact geopolitical dynamics (Lust 2024). In this context, Lithuania's foreign policy behaviour is sometimes perceived as irrational for a state of its size, within the academic debate, due to steps such as labelling Russia a terrorist state (Park and Jakstaite-Confortola 2021) or opening the Taiwan Representation Office in Vilnius (Lust 2024). This demonstrates that Lithuania consistently exhibits behaviour exceeding its structural weight in foreign policy (Lingevičius 2019), which is also often considered a case of regional leadership within the domestic discourse (Andrijauskas 2024).

Similarly, *vis-à-vis* China, Lithuania in qualitative terms stands in a profoundly asymmetrical position, whether measured by population, territory or economic weight. Specifically, in the context of the BRI, the relative smallness could be seen as a material constraint as Lithuania could not negotiate better access to exports to China, and the trade deficit remained unbalanced. However, it could also serve as a form of flexibility. Due to limited exposure to China regarding trade dependence, Lithuania had relatively little to lose in terms of economic impact from a potential spat with China (Andrijauskas 2020), allowing it to adopt a more assertive stance.

The academic debate on Lithuania as a small state often centres on its position towards Russia or in relation to the Baltic states. The Sino-Lithuanian relations have previously been analysed as part of the focus on security concerns of the Baltic states (Berzina-Cerenkova 2021; Scott 2018), or from the perspective of China and its evolving approach to the Baltics (Collins and O'Brien 2023; Larçon 2017). The value-based foreign policy and the subsequent diplomatic spat over the Taiwan Office in Vilnius attracted academic and policy research, either from Lithuania's foreign policy perspective (e.g. Lust 2024; Šimelytė, Struca, and Sadauskis 2024) or the economic security perspective, due to China's coercive measures taken against Lithuania (Andrijauskas and Boruta 2025). The Indo-Pacific strategy has received relatively little attention in academic literature thus far. However, Andrijauskas (2024) demonstrated that Lithuania has successfully exercised agency through its Indo-Pacific turn in values-based foreign policy, aimed at preserving the liberal international order. This paper builds on the previous research by tracing the evolution of Lithuania's engagement with China. It shows how its initial pursuit of economic opportunities

through the BRI shifted toward a securitised perspective on Chinese investment. At the same time, Lithuania leveraged its agency to affiliate with the Indo-Pacific concept, using normative and discursive strategies to maintain economic diversification and enhance its international visibility despite geographic and material constraints.

Conceptual and Methodological Framework: Exploring Space, Power, Governance

The analytical framework of this special issue centres on the interrelated concepts of space, governance and power to explain how states navigate and reshape their international environments. Space refers to the imagined and material geographies through which states construct and express their external relations. It encompasses both physical infrastructure, trade routes, transport corridors and logistical hubs, as well as discursive spaces that define belonging and identity (Lambach 2022). Participation in transregional frameworks such as the BRI or the Indo-Pacific reflects more than economic calculation; it constitutes a spatial strategy that situates states within broader geopolitical imaginaries (Chong and Pham 2020). Shifts in spatial framing can alter how actors perceive opportunities, vulnerabilities and alignments.

Simultaneously, Lithuania's engagement with the BRI unfolded within the broader regulatory and institutional framework of the EU, which shaped the terms of governance and constrained the scope of Chinese-led infrastructure or investment projects (Comerma 2024). Within the EU, governance is facilitated through a complex network of rules and standards governing transparency, procurement and sustainability. This regulatory framework not only constrains external actors, such as China, from pursuing certain forms of influence but also shapes how member states articulate their participation in global initiatives. Compared with regions characterised by looser oversight, such as the Western Balkans, EU governance mechanisms mitigate risks of dependency or political interference, embedding external cooperation within a rules-based order (Berisha and Cotella 2021).

Ultimately, power in this framework is not limited to material capacity but encompasses the ability of states to exercise agency through normative positioning, strategic alignment and discursive entrepreneurship. Small states can project influence by aligning with broader coalitions, articulating principled positions and leveraging international norms to amplify their visibility (e.g. Long 2016; Thorhallsson 2019). Their foreign policy choices thus reveal how agency can emerge within asymmetrical power relations, transforming participation or withdrawal from initiatives like the BRI into acts of strategic signalling.

The paper employs a single case study design, focusing on Lithuania as a divergent case within the broader CEE context. The research is based on thirteen semi-structured interviews conducted in January/February 2025 with a diverse group of actors directly involved in or closely observing Lithuania's evolving foreign policy. These include two academic experts, four current and former officials from the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Ministry of Trade, three diplomatic service members based in Lithuania and Brussels, two members of parliament and two analysts from governmental and independent think tanks. The interviews complement the analysis of official documents and were triangulated with public statements and academic research, as well as additional interviews conducted in the other 16+1 countries. This study uses an inductive approach. By analysing Lithuania's engagement with and withdrawal from the BRI and its alignment with the Indo-Pacific framework, patterns of strategic behaviour and normative positioning were identified.

The study covers the period from 2012 to 2025, with a focus on Lithuania's shifting approach to the BRI and the Indo-Pacific strategy. While there were other key events in the process of shifting Lithuania's approach to China, such as the case of the Taiwanese embassy in Vilnius or the Huawei ban, these are mentioned more briefly to foreground the specific discursive and strategic shift from the BRI to the Indo-Pacific. While domestic political dynamics considerations also shaped Lithuania's approach to China and the BRI, these aspects fall beyond the primary scope of this paper. They are also considered only in less detail. The analysis instead focuses on the external dimension of Lithuania's foreign policy, in line with the research questions, which centre on the country's international positioning, spatial linkages and agency.

Unmet Economic Aspirations: Lithuania's engagement with the BRI

The BRI is widely recognised as a highly contested concept, defined and perceived differently across political, institutional and geographic contexts. While officially framed by Beijing as a development-oriented effort to enhance global infrastructure connectivity, trade integration and economic cooperation, the BRI lacks a centralised institutional framework (Breslin 2021; Miskimmon, O'Loughlin, and Zeng 2021). This flexibility has allowed China to tailor the initiative to varying local conditions and priorities, resulting in a heterogeneous network of bilateral agreements, investment projects and diplomatic forums (Berlie 2020; Chen 2021).

Although Europe was not envisioned as a specific focus of the BRI (Shi and Trigkas 2021), over time, even smaller countries in the region began to gain strategic importance within the initiative due to their particular infrastructural or geographic advantages. During its early

engagement with the BRI, Lithuania was perceived as a peripheral yet potentially valuable connection, mainly due to the port of Klaipėda. As Andrijauskas (2020, 5) argues, the geographical position which borders Belarus and Russia (through Kaliningrad), two Chinese partners, and Lithuanian membership in the EU and the North Atlantic Treaty Organisation (NATO) ‘would at least suggest Chinese economic and political interest in accessing the developed markets and normative communities in the region through yet another of its actors’.

Lithuania’s initial involvement with the BRI followed a similar trajectory to that of other CEE states. Lithuania sought to diversify its trade relations and viewed China as a potential economic partner, particularly in attracting investment for infrastructure development, with proposed Chinese investments in airlines, Kaunas Airport and the Klaipėda port (Vilpišauskas 2023; Interview #1; Interview #3). In 2012, Lithuania joined the 16+1 format, which was later followed by a memorandum of understanding on the BRI. Despite some criticism at the EU level aimed at the BRI (e.g. Prasad 2018), the Lithuanian government pursued participation with the expectation of material economic benefits. Over the following years, however, the absolute value of Chinese investment in Lithuania remained modest. These investments focused on strategic sectors, particularly ports, logistics, and manufacturing, and reflected broader regional patterns. As in much of the CEE region, the scale of investment remained relatively limited, yet it increased steadily. In 2020, China was Lithuania’s thirteenth largest trading partner, with Lithuania’s exports to China accounting for 1% of total exports, while imports from China totalled 4% of total imports (Cutler and Wester 2024). Although some Chinese investments did materialise, these remained modest and, in some cases, controversial (Andrijauskas 2020).

In the domestic discourse, these proposed projects were often framed in terms of economic opportunity and increased cooperation with China, as a potential means of accessing a newly opening market, specifically emphasising the improvement of conditions for Lithuanian agricultural exports to China (Vilpišauskas 2023). This orientation was driven in part by Lithuania’s structural economic needs. As a small, export-oriented economy with limited domestic capital, Lithuania sought to attract foreign investment and expand access to non-EU markets. Transport and logistics were key strategic assets, bolstered by the country’s geographic position, with the port of Klaipėda as the vital access point (Lust 2024). As the Minister of Transport put it: “China is the biggest Asian market; therefore, Lithuania’s goal to become an important economic partner with China is natural and unavoidable,” stressing that: “the long-term goals of this project are to entrench Lithuania’s role as a transit centre between the Far East and Europe, in the global logistics chain” (Gerdžiūnas 2020).

Despite these ambitions, this phase of cooperation was structurally uneven, and trade remained unbalanced. Lithuania consistently ran substantial trade deficits with China, primarily due to an asymmetry in market access. Lithuanian firms found it difficult to access the Chinese market, despite the ongoing negotiations at the political level (Vilpišauskas 2023). Although bilateral agreements were signed in the agriculture, logistics and investment sectors, the outcomes often fell short of expectations. Despite these limitations, discussions about Chinese investment persisted. In 2017, Lithuanian authorities continued to express interest in attracting Chinese investments into Klaipeda, the country's largest container port (Vilpišauskas 2023). Lithuania initially sought to utilise the BRI as a vehicle for economic diversification and to strengthen its role as a logistics hub. The strategic significance of Klaipeda was central to Chinese infrastructure proposals, which focused on developing a deep-sea terminal that could link to the China-funded Great Stone Industrial Park in neighbouring Belarus. Yet, despite repeated negotiations, no agreement was reached. Lithuania's unwillingness to cede control of the strategic infrastructure was a core sticking point (Andrijauskas 2020; Lust 2024). As several interviewees noted, the unmet expectations created an opportunity for recalibrating the perspective on China (e.g., Interview #1; Interview #2; Interview #7).

As the anticipated investments failed to materialise, the associated concerns about normative influence or governance conditionalities did not pose the risks initially feared. This was due, in part, to the EU's regulatory framework, which limited China's capacity to exert governance influence through investment (Ghiretti 2021). Moreover, the 2009 mandate, which empowered the European Commission to negotiate investment agreements on behalf of all member states, already diluted the potential for bilateral entanglement (European Commission 2025). In contrast to, for example, the Western Balkans, where such frameworks do not apply, and governance of the projects is more affected, leading to risks of corruption or environmental damages (Tsimonis et al. 2019; Vangeli and Pavličević 2019), Lithuania remained embedded within a legal and institutional order that constrained external leverage (Berzina-Cerenkova 2021). As Comerma (2024, 7) argues, the main impact of the BRI

has been a general paradigm shift in connectivity and infrastructure development policy. "It is the end of the notion that investment flows are neutral"; the BRI has manifested that investment flows "have a security aspect that just needs to be taken care of".

Rethinking Cooperation with China: from Economic Opportunity to Security Threat

This paradigm shift was evident in the case of Lithuania, where, in 2018–2019, a gradual change emerged in the political discourse regarding the BRI. What had previously been framed in economic and commercial terms was increasingly interpreted through the lens of risks, especially national security. By 2018, high-level political figures had started to raise concerns about potential problems connected to possible interference through investments alongside the BRI. Then-Minister of Foreign Affairs, Linas Linkevičius, publicly emphasised the need for Lithuania to retain strategic control over key infrastructure and suggested that Chinese investments should be evaluated on economic grounds and with a clear view toward security implications (Vilpišauskas 2023, 87).

Domestic institutions echoed this evolving security-oriented framing. In 2019, the State Security Department (VSD) addressed China extensively in its National Security Threat Assessment, compared to the previous year (State Security Department of the Republic of Lithuania 2019), warning of expanded Chinese intelligence services operating in Lithuania. The same year, Lithuanian President Gitanas Nausėdas said that Chinese investment in the Klaipėda port can undermine national and European security (BNS 2019). Moreover, Defence Minister Raimundas Karoblis directly framed potential Chinese investment in the port as a strategic liability for NATO (Gerdžiūnas 2020). Marius Laurinavičius, analyst at Vilnius Policy Analysis Institute, noted some pressure from the United States towards Lithuania regarding Huawei's presence in 5G infrastructure development and Chinese investments in Klaipėda (Gerdžiūnas 2020). This shows that apart from some initial fears of Chinese normative influence, concerns emerged about direct interference of Chinese actors through investments in critical infrastructure. Those were linked specifically to NATO, broader European security and the United States security priorities, which constitute the cornerstone of Lithuania's own national security and foreign policy orientation.

Changing International Context: Borders, Conflicts, and Great-Power Rivalry

The shifting perception of cooperation with China unravelled within a polarising international context. The evolving United States stance on China, marked by escalating tensions during the Trump administration and, to some extent, sustained under Biden, has been one of the critical factors in shaping Lithuania's position on China. For Lithuania, the United States is a key security guarantor through NATO and bilateral defence ties, and a vital reference point for its Euro-Atlantic identity (Lust 2024). Moreover, within the EU, the reactions to BRI also evolved, towards a heightened security perspective, addressing China as a partner, economic competitor and systemic rival in 2019 (European Commission 2019a). As noted by Pugliese, Ghiretti, and Insisa (2022), although the BRI received mixed reactions within the EU, at the beginning, many did not

see the official affiliation as a problematic issue. The threat perception rose over time when critical infrastructure, such as the port of Piraeus in Greece, was concerned, or when the EU member states used the BRI to express anti-EU views, as in the case of the Italian government (Pugliese 2024). This represented a significant discursive shift: from viewing China as an economic partner to perceiving it as a geopolitical actor whose growing presence presented a potential for interference in the security infrastructure (European Commission 2019b).

These developments are particularly critical for Lithuania, given its geographic proximity to Russia. Lithuania's security concerns are closely intertwined with its commitment to NATO and the broader Euro-Atlantic framework, making alignment with the United States and EU partners not only a matter of foreign policy preference but also of existential strategic necessity (Andrijauskas 2024; Lust 2024). Beyond security concerns, Lithuania's geographical position posed additional complications for deeper engagement with Chinese connectivity frameworks. As a transit country, Lithuania's links to Central Asia and China necessarily run through Belarus and Russia, two increasingly problematic neighbours. The re-election of Alexander Lukashenko in Belarus in 2020, followed by widespread protests and a harsh crackdown, led Lithuania to adopt a strong oppositional stance. Vilnius took the lead in EU calls for sanctions and publicly supported the Belarusian opposition (Bukovskis and Livdanska 2024). These actions effectively froze connectivity through Belarus and, by extension, complicated any deeper involvement in BRI-related infrastructure initiatives. The COVID-19 pandemic and, subsequently, Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in early 2022 further hindered the possibility of infrastructural developments.

Values-Driven Foreign Policy: Lithuania's New Approach to China

A significant turning point in Lithuania's China policy came with the inauguration of the new centre-right government in late 2020. The incoming coalition explicitly committed to a values-based foreign policy. This shift was not simply rhetorical; it entailed a substantive reorientation in tone and practice. China was no longer framed primarily as an economic partner or neutral geopolitical actor. Instead, it increasingly became understood as a strategic and systemic rival (Ferenczy 2022). The most visible manifestations of this reorientation came in two key moves: Lithuania's withdrawal from the 17+1 format (EurActiv, LRT 2021) and the decision to allow the opening of the Taiwanese Representative Office in Vilnius in 2021 (MFA 2021), using the name 'Taiwan' rather than 'Taipei'. Both moves marked significant breaks with prior policy.

The decision to open the Taiwanese Representative Office triggered Beijing's immediate and forceful response. China downgraded diplomatic relations with Lithuania to the level of *chargé*

d'affaires and implemented a series of informal but highly effective trade restrictions (Andrijauskas and Boruta 2025). Lithuanian exports to China dropped by more than 80% in early 2022 compared to the previous year (European Commission 2022). In response, Lithuania received support from key allies. The EU initiated a case at the World Trade Organisation (WTO), arguing that China's actions constituted discriminatory and coercive trade practices (European Commission 2022). In parallel, the United States publicly backed Lithuania's position and, according to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA) and Lithuanian Parliament officials, worked to facilitate alternative trade routes and offered diplomatic support (Reuters 2022; Interview #8; Interview #10). Thus, providing the role of economic and political shelters (Thorhallsson 2019).

Within this process, Lithuania did not formally cancel its Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) on the BRI. However, as several officials noted in the interviews, the MoU was not legally binding and contained few, if any, concrete commitments (Interview #1; Interview #2). In practical terms, the departure from 17+1 was far more consequential, symbolically and politically. By exiting the platform, Lithuania signalled its disillusionment with the initiative and unwillingness to participate in future cooperation. One interviewee highlighted that 'leaving 17+1 showed that we were serious and wanted to limit any contact with China' (Interview #5). This is congruent with the statement of the Prime Minister, Landsbergis, who advocated for "a much more effective 27+1 approach and communication with China" and called the 17+1 "divisive" (EurActiv, p.4 LRT p.2 2021). Exiting 17+1, Lithuania was followed by the other two Baltic states, with Lithuania enforcing its profile as a regional leader (Andrijauskas 2024). The 14+1 is now often deemed frozen or inactive (e.g. Ciurtin 2022; Hulička 2023; Interview #6). For many remaining countries, exiting the format is not considered worth the potential diplomatic costs. For example, as one Czech official from the MFA noted, 'the cooperation within the 14+1 is mostly stalled, but we remain members to observe and to have the chance to prevent some undesirable decisions if necessary' (Interview #6).

The new government entered office with a clear, values-based foreign policy orientation, already evident in the coalition agreement (Euractiv 2020) and in the winning party's electoral manifesto (IS-LKD 2020, 64). However, the subsequent turn in China policy, including the decision to allow the establishment of the Taiwanese Representative Office, remained controversial. It was pursued despite divisions within the political elite and contrary to the preferences of much of the public. For example, President Gitanas Nausėda publicly criticised the naming of the office as a "mistake" and noted that the decision had not been coordinated with him (LRT 2022, p.1). Former President Valdas Adamkus likewise argued that the policy was ill-

judged, stressing that a small state such as Lithuania should not take the lead in recognising Taiwan in this manner (BNS 2022). Public opinion data also showed a majority opposing the government's approach and favouring prioritisation of economic cooperation with China over symbolic values-based actions (BNS 2024). Overall, this indicates that the government prioritised a values-based shift, rather than responding to a broad public mandate or a consensus among Lithuania's political leadership.

Projecting Agency: Alignment with the Indo-Pacific Concept

Following the reorientation of its China policy, Lithuania became the first and only Baltic state to formally adopt an Indo-Pacific strategy, with most of the interviewees viewing it as a continuation of the new policy direction taken on China. All interviewees perceived the strategy in light of the value-based foreign policy and as a way to conceptualise China within the larger region. This framing is congruent with the concept promoted by the United States and adopted in various forms by allies such as the EU, Canada, and Australia. For Lithuania, this concept provided a valuable platform for positioning itself among like-minded democracies, although its direct capabilities in the Indo-Pacific are limited. The timing of the strategy's publication, just ahead of the NATO Summit in Vilnius in July 2023, was a clear signal to its Euro-Atlantic allies, particularly the United States, of its commitment to shared security concerns. All interviews mentioned this timing as an important strategic choice for the MFA to publish the strategy, as the critical international partners were present in Vilnius. This shows that the strategy was not only aimed at the audience within the geographical Indo-Pacific region, as defined in the strategy.

Officials involved in the development of the strategy highlighted multiple motivations. One was the desire to remain attuned to global developments and adopt the emerging terminology of the Indo-Pacific, signalling awareness and responsiveness to shifting international discourses. This goal was explicitly connected to alignment with key allies within NATO, and secondly, the EU. The goal included future coordination on agendas on Indo-Pacific within Lithuanian-United States bilateral discussions (Interview #1; Interview #3). The strategy was consulted with United States and Canadian or EU counterparts, which opened avenues for alignment with key partners. While on one hand, the interest of the United States in the Indo-Pacific served as a pragmatic motivating factor for increased involvement in the Indo-Pacific, the partnership also helped Lithuania to connect with regional partners, as that would oftentimes be difficult for a smaller country on its own (Interview #1; Interview #3; Interview #7). Moreover, the strategy and its implementation prompted Lithuania to join an informal EU network of countries focused on the

Indo-Pacific. This fostered greater contact and closer alignment among the member states involved, allowing Lithuania also to be part of the discussion at this level (Interview #5).

Moreover, by explicitly supporting Taiwan while taking a firm stance on China, Lithuania projected itself as a principled actor and further promoted its values-based policy. Comparatively, the strategy is harsher on China, and the government aimed to promote further economic cooperation based on shared values. Thus, the original purpose envisioned for the BRI was to connect to new markets, increase trade relations, attract investments, and enhance people-to-people exchanges, thereby boosting the domestic economy and adding a layer of diversification from China. As argued by Lust (2024), opening the Taiwanese Office can be seen as motivated by three main actors: diversification of external economic relations, identity and niche-building. Apart from the aim of attracting new investments from Taiwan, Lithuania diverges from the other Baltic countries in its identity as the first one of the three that announced independence on the USSR. Moreover, it lacks a specific niche. Thus, the values-based policy, oriented on security and firm stance on China, could serve as a strategic niche in Lithuania's foreign policy. This argument is congruent with the interviews, which specifically mentioned identity and geographical specialisation as one of the factors behind the Indo-pacific strategy (Interview #2; Interview #5).

However, establishing cooperation with countries in the Indo-Pacific will take a considerable amount of time. It was thus underlined that cooperation with the United States is vital in this sense, as it has been able to 'open some doors' (Interview #2; Interview #3). Although most interviewees considered the strategy's publication a success, its practical implementation is limited by budgetary constraints, diplomatic capacities, or a lack of expertise on the region within the public service, a hurdle shared by other small states in the EU (Interview #6; Interview #12). Nevertheless, there is sustained interest in implementing the strategy. Even before its publication, Lithuania expanded its presence in the region by opening embassies in Australia, South Korea, and Singapore between 2020 and 2022, and established a strategic partnership with Japan (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Lithuania 2024).

Lithuania has taken practical steps to operationalise its Indo-Pacific engagement, for example, by appointing a special envoy for Indo-Pacific 23/02/2026 13:19:00. According to the interviews, the government is further interested in expanding relations mainly with South Korea and India, with enhanced cultural and academic ties. Moreover, the Lithuanian MFA monitors the implementation of the strategy, preparing an action plan for the next three years, while assessing the last action plan that accompanied the strategic plan (Interview #5; Interview #11). However, the funding and resource allocation remain limited. These efforts and the interviews confirm that

while Lithuania's capacity may be limited, it is not engaging in the Indo-Pacific purely for symbolic purposes (Andrijauskas 2024).

The focus on Indo-Pacific and the values-based policy was tied to the centre-right government. Current indicators suggest no significant shift, but a move towards normalisation of relations with China. In 2024, the government in Lithuania changed, and the new government confirmed that it would continue with the established foreign policy direction. However, the government must cope with the region's realities and the changing global landscape. For example, the government is exploring possibilities to enhance trade relations with Vietnam, which may be challenging under the value-based rhetoric. Moreover, with the second presidency of Donald Trump, some actors within the EU are more vocal about possible increased cooperation with China, and the Lithuanian PM Gintautas Paluckas has already expressed the willingness to restore diplomatic relations with China (Sokolovskis 2025). Lastly, in August 2025, there was another government change, as Prime Minister Gintautas Paluckas resigned due to a corruption scandal and was replaced by Inga Ruginienė, a member of the Social Democrats. She formed a coalition with the populist party Nemunas Dawn and the Greens, and the new government has signalled a more pragmatic China policy, seeking to reset diplomatic relations while still recognising Beijing as a security challenge (Peseckyte 2025).

Both broader EU dynamics and domestic public opinion reinforced the new government's return to a more pragmatic China policy. In early 2025, debates emerged within the EU about whether the bloc should adjust its stance toward China, as several actors argued that Trump's renewed isolationism created both economic risks and strategic incentives to reinforce engagement with Beijing. For example, the Spanish government publicly called for increased cooperation with China shortly after the start of Trump's second term. (Basteiro and Orihuela 2025; Everts 2025). Moreover, this was also in accordance with public opinion in Lithuania, which largely viewed the previous direction taken on China as too harsh (BNS 2024). Although the Lithuanian public perceives China as a threat, it also views it as a significant economic power. Thus, generally, the public perception of Lithuania as a small country also informs the idea that Lithuania should not take an overly critical stance on China. This, in turn, also allowed the incoming government to place less emphasis on values-based policy in its overall approach (Merkinaitė et al. 2024).

Discussion: Navigating Power, Space, and Governance

Lithuania's initial engagement and later disengagement from the BRI reshaped its external linkages across diplomatic, economic and normative dimensions. While early participation

reflected an attempt to position Lithuania within broader Eurasian trade and connectivity networks, this aspiration was constrained by structural realities and evolving political priorities. As the geopolitical context evolved and expectations of deeper economic cooperation with China remained unmet, the perceived opportunities diminished. Once the framing of China shifted, the BRI was no longer seen as a neutral infrastructure corridor but as a potential security threat.

With the turn towards the Indo-Pacific, Lithuania was able to utilise its spatial imaginary to reconstruct its geopolitical space and employ it as a diplomatic tool. The government was able to re-embed its external linkages within a community of like-minded democracies, reinforce its transatlantic identity, and signal reliability to the United States and other partners in the EU or Indo-Pacific. These dynamics underscore how the Lithuanian government was able to exercise agency through discourse and identity-driven diplomacy, thereby contributing to broader IR debates on how limited-capacity actors navigate and influence hierarchical international orders through spatial imaginaries. Moreover, this reframing shows that, when deciding between different geopolitical frameworks, it was ultimately more important for Lithuania's government to affiliate based on norms and security than to prioritise potential economic repercussions.

One of the central findings of this study is that this reframing was driven by domestic political actors whose strong value-based convictions and security-oriented worldviews played a key role, demonstrating how small-state agency can emerge from domestic normative commitments. This elite-driven agency demonstrates how small states mobilise non-material power resources: identity, principles and discursive leadership, to exercise influence. The Lithuanian case thus provides empirical support for the argument that small states can leverage such resources to compensate for material limitations, expanding their capacity to act autonomously or shape international norms (Long 2016). In this sense, it also confirms findings by Andrijauskas (2024), who, in the case of Lithuanian Indo-Pacific strategy, observed 'a remarkable level of small state agency'.

Moreover, the Lithuanian case illustrates that the very material limitations and structural constraints that hindered deeper cooperation with China also strengthened Lithuania's room for manoeuvre. Because Lithuania had limited economic ties with China and the initial engagement did not significantly increase them, it faced fewer costs in shifting course. This relative freedom from dependency became a source of agency, enabling the government to pursue a more assertively value-based foreign policy. While larger or more economically intertwined states may face higher opportunity costs when confronting China, Lithuania's low level of economic exposure

enabled it to shift decisively from engagement to normative contestation. This flexibility became a strategic resource, permitting the governing elite to pursue value-based foreign policy.

In terms of governance, Lithuania's initial engagement with the BRI unfolded within the broader regulatory and institutional framework of the EU, which shaped the terms of external cooperation and constrained the scope of Chinese-led infrastructure or investment projects. EU standards on transparency, procurement and environmental compliance curtailed the implementation of BRI initiatives in Lithuania (Comerma 2024). As a result, governance problems that were visible in states outside the EU, such as in the Western Balkans, where Chinese projects often raised concerns over corruption, weak oversight and political influence, were far less salient within the EU context (Tsimonis et al. 2019). The EU's regulatory environment thus not only limited the reach of Chinese influence but also embedded external cooperation within a rules-based order, aligning it with broader European governance practices. Moreover, the BRI projects have not materialised due to security concerns on the Lithuanian side, which halted any significant investment in key infrastructure even before it occurred. Through the frame of security, Lithuania was able to limit the scope for BRI-related governance questions to emerge at all, with projects halted before concrete oversight mechanisms were required. At the same time, the Lithuanian case suggests that it remains challenging to determine what BRI governance would have looked like in practice, as both EU-level constraints and national security concerns hindered project development at an early stage.

Conclusion

This article examines how Lithuania's engagement with, and eventual rejection of, the BRI have reshaped its external linkages and strategic orientation. The analysis has shown that Lithuania's initial participation reflected pragmatic economic opportunity and connectivity calculations. As a small, export-oriented economy with limited capital, engagement in the BRI was framed as a way to diversify markets and benefit from transnational flows. Yet over time, the lack of tangible economic gains, rising geopolitical risks and normative tensions prompted a fundamental reconfiguration of Lithuania's spatial outlook. Rather than continuing to situate itself within Eurasian connectivity frameworks, Lithuania shifted its focus toward the Indo-Pacific, opening new diplomatic representations, establishing strategic partnerships, and solidifying its presence within transatlantic and rules-based networks.

Moreover, the findings suggest that Lithuania's power has not stemmed from material capacity, but from the strategic use of discourse, normative alignment and domestic agency. By

reframing China as a security risk and repositioning itself as an advocate of democratic norms and rules-based order, Lithuania leveraged reputational and symbolic tools to gain visibility on the global stage. In this sense, Lithuania demonstrates that small states can amplify their presence by selectively engaging with competing international projects, not as passive recipients but as actors capable of redefining the frameworks within which they operate. At the same time, the Lithuanian case highlights the limits of such agency. Budgetary and diplomatic constraints remain significant, and the sustainability of new Indo-Pacific linkages will depend on the ability to institutionalise them within governance frameworks and to maintain long-term political consensus.

As an inductive single-case analysis, this study inevitably faces limitations. Its insights cannot be generalised across all small states, as others may encounter different domestic constraints, structural pressures or regional dynamics. Nevertheless, Lithuania offers an instructive example of how a small state can recalibrate its external linkages when navigating between competing geopolitical frameworks. Within the special issue, it represents a divergent case: a state that not only disengaged from the BRI but reframed its geopolitical orientation by mobilising spatial imaginaries and value-based diplomacy. Lithuania's case illuminates how small states reassess opportunities and risks as geopolitical contexts evolve. The case underscores that small states weigh alternative frameworks not merely through material cost–benefit calculations, but also through normative alignment and security considerations that they deem essential to their long-term survival. In this way, the Lithuanian experience demonstrates that domestic political actors, identity-driven diplomacy, and limited material exposure can together enable significant agency.

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The Complete List of Interviews

Interview #1 – Civil servant, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Lithuania

Interview #2 – Former official, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Lithuania

Interview #3 – Member of the Seimas, Lithuanian Christian Democrat Political Group

Interview #4 – Geopolitics and Security Studies Centre (GSSC), Lithuania

Interview #5 – Diplomatic Service of the Republic of Lithuania

Interview #6 – Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic, Department of Asia and the Pacific

Interview #7 – Academic, Vytautas Magnus University, Kaunas

Interview #8 – Academic, Vilnius University

Interview #9 – Diplomatic Service of the Republic of Lithuania, based in Brussels

Interview #10 – Ministry of Economy and Innovation of the Republic of Lithuania

Interview #11 – Government Strategic Analysis Centre, STRATA

Interview #12 – NATO diplomat

Interview #13 – Former official, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Lithuania